

Data-Driven and Evidence-Based Computing Algorithms to Detect Anomalies of Cycling Facilities

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Abstract. This paper explores the development of a data-driven, evidence-based approach to manage the quality of cycling facilities, focusing on detecting anomalies based on vibration data collected from different road types. We introduce a method for reconstructing normal vibration patterns from mixed datasets, demonstrating the model's ability to capture smooth and bumpy road conditions, as well as the challenges posed by sloped surfaces. A statistical threshold for anomaly detection is defined by combining accelerometer, gyroscope, and speed data, providing a comprehensive approach to identifying anomalous vibrations. Results show that the computing model can effectively distinguish between normal and anomalous data across various road conditions, offering a robust solution for managing cycling infrastructure with real-time, data-driven insights.

Keywords. Bike infrastructure, Anomaly detection, Machine learning

1. Introduction

The promotion of cycling as a sustainable and healthy mode of transportation has gained significant momentum in recent years, with numerous urban planning and public health initiatives advocating for cycling as a viable alternative to traditional modes of transport. The instrumented bicycle developed by Ho et al. (2024) offers an economical and efficient method for

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assessing the condition of bicycle lanes and detecting anomalies. The handlebars of the instrumented bicycle are equipped with two smartphones running different operating systems, while a GoPro camera is installed to record the road surface conditions during the ride. The smartphones collect data on acceleration, gyroscope, speed, GPS, and mobile signal using their embedded sensors. Machine learning algorithms can be applied to identify hazardous locations such as cracks, potholes, and manholes. The anomaly information is then displayed on a Geographic Information System (GIS) map. This paper introduces a hybrid model combining bidirectional LSTM and VQ-VAE for detecting anomalies in bicycle lanes.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data Collection

Data collection was carried out using two smartphones: an iPhone 14 Pro and a Samsung S10. These devices were positioned on the bicycle, with their locations indicated in the figure 1. The smartphones collected data through their embedded sensors, including acceleration, gravity acceleration, gyroscope readings, GPS location, and timestamps, which are exported as a .csv file.

Figure 1. Instrumented bike setup

During the data collection process, the cyclist was instructed to maintain a steady speed as much as possible. Additionally, the cyclist was directed not to avoid road anomalies such as cracks and potholes, ensuring that the data accurately represented the real conditions of the road.

2.2. Data Preprocessing

After data collection, the next step was data processing, aimed at generating smoother vibration signals and creating sliding window sequences.

The processing began by applying Euler's formula (eq. 1) to transform the smartphone's coordinate system to align with that of the bicycle.

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_x'' \\ a_y'' \\ a_z'' \end{bmatrix} = R_z(\gamma)R_y(\beta)R_x(\alpha) \begin{bmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\gamma & -\sin\gamma & 0 \\ \sin\gamma & \cos\gamma & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos\beta & 0 & \sin\beta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin\beta & 0 & \cos\beta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos\alpha & -\sin\alpha \\ 0 & \sin\alpha & \cos\alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{bmatrix} \quad eq. 1$$

Subsequently, both a Gaussian filter and a Butterworth filter were used to smooth the data, with a sampling frequency of 100Hz and a cutoff frequency of 0.5Hz to eliminate abrupt starts or stops. Finally, overlapping subsequences were generated from the processed samples, preparing the data for input into the time series network in subsequent steps. The window size is set to 21 to ensure sufficient timely information.

2.3. Computing Model Reconstruction

The computing model proposed in this paper combines a bidirectional long short-term memory (Bi-LSTM) network with a vector quantized variational autoencoder (VQ-VAE). The primary objective of constructing this network is to utilize the neural network to reconstruct a smooth vibration signal that accurately represents the road surface. The neural network structure is illustrated in Figure 2. For the encoder, two Bi-LSTM layers are employed to capture temporal information and dependencies within the data.

Following this, VQ-VAE is applied to transform continuous data into discrete data. This approach is chosen to eliminate unnecessary data, allowing the model to focus more effectively on key features. Essentially, the training dataset is a mixed set containing both normal and abnormal data. By utilizing this mechanism, the model is able to extract features from the normal data while still being able to handle anomalies.

Figure 2. network architecture

Since Bi-LSTM can consider both past and future states, rather than only focusing on preceding states, using a Bi-LSTM as the encoder is advantageous for capturing temporal features (Oak et al., 2024). This allows the model to develop a more comprehensive context for the data. In other words, the bidirectional LSTM enhances the model's ability to understand the overall trend of the data, allowing it to filter out anomalies related to short-term behaviors, such as sudden stops or human interference.

After encoding the data with the Bi-LSTM, VQ-VAE is used to construct the codebook for the data, which aids in detecting road anomalies by compressing the signal. VQ-VAE is capable of building a codebook that compresses and extracts features from the data (Oord et al., 2018). The effectiveness of the codebook is assessed through the codebook loss, which is based on cosine distance as the loss function. This focus on the trend of change, rather than on exact numerical differences, helps the model capture important patterns like acceleration and deceleration, while being less sensitive to short-term, sudden behaviors (such as emergency stops or human driving actions). Consequently, VQ-VAE proves more accurate in detecting road anomalies.

Given that the data in the codebook is high-dimensional compressed data, the decoder is required to translate this into readable information, a process referred to as the decoding process. This process is akin to a translation, relying solely on the previously generated steps and the codebook, without considering future information. Therefore, an LSTM is employed as the decoder, which is subsequently connected to a fully connected layer to produce the final outputs.

3. Anomaly Detection

The proposed model can generate normal data vibrations from the mixed dataset. In *figure 3*, it shows the vibration patterns for a smoother road surface. The blue line represents the normalized acceleration, while the yellow line shows the reconstructed vibration. The reconstructed vibration patterns are much smoother.

Figure 3 Reconstructed vibration signal

Based on the reconstructed smooth road surface, bike road anomalies can distinguish by a given threshold, which is automatically calculated by eq. 2.

$$\text{THR} = \frac{1}{D} \sum_{i=1}^D \text{Err}(x_i) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{D} \sum_{i=1}^D (\text{Err}(x_i) - \mu)^2} \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

where we denote $\text{Err}(x_i)$ as the sum of loss function for x_i , and μ is the average value of $\text{Err}(x_i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, D$. The setting is similar to the normal training distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$ following with 1 standard deviation σ of the mean μ .

Additionally, *figure 3* only shows the normalized 3D acceleration. However, anomaly detection does not rely solely on this; it also takes into account the gyroscope and speed. A point is considered anomalous only when all three—acceleration, gyroscope, and speed—simultaneously exceed the threshold for anomalies. An example of using simultaneous analyses is shown in *figure 4*.

Figure 4. Detected anomalies

4. Conclusion

In this study, we have successfully demonstrated a method for reconstructing and analyzing bike vibrations to identify anomalies based on a multi-sensor approach. By utilizing data from accelerometers, gyroscopes, and speed sensors, we established a statistical threshold to detect anomalies with higher accuracy. This research provides a potential solution for developing data-driven, evidence-based strategies to enhance the management of cycling infrastructure, contributing to more efficient and safer cycling experiences. Future work could explore further optimization of the model and its application in different environments.

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